

Black Soldier Fly (BSF): A Sustainable Solution for Protein, Waste Management, and a Circular Bio-Economy

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Abstract:

The Black Soldier Fly (BSF) is emerging as a game-changer in the animal feed industry and waste management. This article explores the potential of BSF larvae as a sustainable, high-protein feed source for various animals, including fish, poultry, and pigs. It delves into open and closed BSF production systems, highlighting their advantages and considerations. Furthermore, the article details the diverse products derived from BSF, including larvae, oil, and protein meal, showcasing their applications in animal feed formulations. The concept of a BSF circular economy is introduced, emphasizing its potential for fostering resource conservation, ecological stewardship,

and cascading environmental benefits. Finally, the article discusses the challenges and opportunities associated with BSF production and integration into the animal feed sector.

Keywords: *Black Soldier Fly, Animal Feed, Sustainable Protein source, Circular Economy.*

Introduction

Global population projections estimate a staggering 9.6 billion people by 2050. To meet this growing demand, the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) predicts a 70% increase in food production, with meat production requiring a doubling in beef, poultry, and pork. This anticipated rise in population translates to a projected increase in demand for meat and seafood, potentially driving the expansion of the aquaculture industry. In response to consumer concerns about sustainability and the environmental impact of traditional meat

production, food manufacturers are actively developing novel alternative protein sources as substitutes for muscle meat (Higa, Ruby, & Rozin, 2021). Livestock production, particularly muscle meat from animals like cattle, presents a significant threat to global ecosystems (Lamb et al., 2021). This industry is responsible for a substantial portion of global resource consumption, using an estimated 30% of the world's land and 8% of its freshwater (Lamb et al., 2021). Additionally, livestock production generates greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions exceeding those from the transportation sector, accounting for 14.5% of global emissions.

Furthermore, cattle production is a major contributor to environmental problems like eutrophication (nutrient overload in water bodies) and deforestation, which are estimated to contribute 34% of total agricultural GHG emissions (Siddiqui et al., 2022). Thankfully, the circular economy offers solutions, and Black Soldier Fly (BSF) emerges as a promising new approach. The use of Black Soldier Flies (BSF) for waste management aligns seamlessly with the principles of a circular economy. This innovative process transforms organic waste streams into valuable protein sources embodied by the insects themselves (van Huis & Oonincx, 2017).

By diverting waste from landfills and converting it into a usable resource, BSF bioconversion exemplifies a sustainable approach within the circular economy framework. A comprehensive review by Wang and Shelomi (Wang & Shelomi, 2017) highlights the environmental benefits of using insects as a protein source for farm animals. They found that raising insects on human-inedible waste is more sustainable than using valuable resources like land, water, and energy to produce human food directly (Wang & Shelomi, 2017). Nevertheless, large-scale production of insect-based proteins might offer a viable substitute for animal meat since it demands less land, generates minimal greenhouse gases, and has low competition for feed resources.

Several factors make insects a promising alternative protein source for animal feed. Their high nutritional value, including essential amino acids and lipids (Makkar, 2018), combined with minimal space requirements for rearing, suggest a potentially more sustainable approach than traditional feed crops (Rehman et al., 2023).

Additionally, studies have demonstrated the palatability and digestibility of insects by various livestock species, including fish, poultry, and reptiles, which naturally consume insects in their diets (Makkar, 2018). Furthermore, insect production offers potential advantages beyond nutrition. Their high feed conversion efficiency (van Huis & Gasco, 2023) and rapid reproductive capabilities translate to potentially lower production costs compared to

conventional protein sources. Moreover, insects can serve as a source of valuable by-products like chitin, and their inclusion in some livestock diets (e.g., fish) aligns with natural feeding patterns (Devi & Kim, 2014). Among various insect species, Black Soldier Fly Larvae (BSFL) of the species *Hermetia illucens* L. (Diptera: *Stratiomyidae*) are considered particularly promising due to their efficient waste conversion and rapid life cycle (van Huis & Gasco, 2023). However, it is important to acknowledge that environmental factors play a role in insect production efficiency, although studies generally indicate a significantly lower land footprint and reduced water and greenhouse gas emissions compared to conventional feed production systems (Rehman et al., 2023).

Ensuring food safety throughout the insect-rearing process remains crucial for successfully commercializing insect-based feed. In that plight, the current EU and US FDA regulations restrict the use of potentially hazardous materials like animal manure and household waste as insect feed. In Europe, insect production primarily relies on leftover food items that don't contain meat or fish and byproducts from non-animal food production. The European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) allows for a broader range of substrates, including food waste of non-animal origin from human consumption and standard animal feed materials (Commission, 2013; Committee, 2015). This opens doors for using discards like fruit and vegetable scraps from markets to raise insects for animal feed, ultimately contributing to the human food chain. Importantly, utilizing food byproducts serves not only as a sustainable animal protein source but also as a waste management solution and a key utilization of the circular economy concept. This review explores BSF's role in the CE, rearing systems, and creating sustainable products.

BSF Production Systems: Open vs. Closed

Two main types of BSF production systems are categorized by how the flies reproduce (Diener,

Lalander, Zurbrugg, & Vinnerås, 2015; Kenis et al., 2018).

Open Systems (OS)

These systems rely on wild BSF to lay eggs in piles of exposed organic waste (S Diener et al., 2015). Newly hatched larvae have a ready food source nearby. Open systems are low-maintenance and require minimal infrastructure. They can be bins, wooden structures, or even just exposed piles of waste (Cappelozza et al., 2019; Cortes Ortiz et al., 2016). Since larvae naturally move to pupate when fully grown, harvesting can involve manually sorting them from the remaining waste material (frass) or letting them migrate out on their own (da Silva & Hesselberg, 2020; Surendra et al., 2020). The first research on open systems involved using wild BSF to convert chicken manure in basins under cages (Zabaleta, Scholten, & Zurbrugg, 2014). There are now many open system designs available online. These systems are typically small-scale and used by hobbyists or small farmers (Cappelozza et al., 2019; Pastor, Velasquez, Gobbi, & Rojo, 2015).

Closed Systems (CS)

These systems offer more control by breeding BSF in captivity. Temperature and humidity are carefully managed to optimize fly production (Cortes Ortiz et al., 2016). Closed systems have two main sections: a breeding unit where adult flies lay eggs, and a separate waste treatment unit where larvae feed on organic waste (Cortes Ortiz et al., 2016). Eggs are collected from the breeding unit and added to the waste. Harvesting methods can range from simple sieving to complex machinery. Closed systems can be small, medium, or large-scale operations (Cortes Ortiz et al., 2016).

The best BSF production system depends on your location and resources. Small and medium-scale insect producers are found worldwide (Nyakeri, Ogola, Ayieko, & Amimo, 2017). These systems are well-suited for areas with inexpensive labor and limited access to protein feed, but there is less research on them compared to larger closed systems (Stefan Diener, Zurbrugg, & Tockner, 2009; Hem,

Toure, Sagbla, & Legendre, 2008). According to the World Bank, most insect farms in Africa are small-scale and open-air, while very few are large-scale and climate-controlled (Cappelozza et al., 2019). While small-scale open systems offer advantages, they can also be unpredictable, have health risks, and may not be profitable in all locations. However, the growing popularity of these systems in developing countries means there is a need to study their environmental impact compared to closed systems.

Products from Black Soldier Fly

This section explores the potential of insects as a sustainable protein source for animal feed. Animal feed plays a critical role in animal husbandry, directly impacting animal health, growth rate, and immune function (Henchion, Moloney, Hyland, Zimmermann, & McCarthy, 2021). With a growing global population and rising meat consumption, the demand for high-quality, sustainable protein sources for animal feed is increasing (FAO, 2021). Traditional protein sources, such as fishmeal, processed animal proteins, and soybean meal, face limitations due to resource scarcity, environmental impact, and regulations (Fumière et al., 2009; Veldkamp et al., 2012).

Insects offer a promising alternative protein source for animal feed production. Their high feed conversion efficiency, ability to be reared on organic waste streams, and cold-blooded metabolism contribute to their sustainability (Veldkamp et al., 2012). Furthermore, insects possess a high protein content (30-70% dry matter) and a favorable amino acid profile (Veldkamp et al., 2012).

Insect Protein in Aquaculture

Insect protein has emerged as a potential replacement for fishmeal and fish oil in aquaculture (Li et al., 2016). Fishmeal and fish oil are crucial protein and fat sources in aqua feeds, but overfishing and resource limitations threaten their sustainability. Studies have demonstrated that Black Soldier Fly Larvae (BSFL) meal can partially or fully replace fishmeal in various fish species with no adverse effects on growth

performance or fillet quality (Cummins et al., 2017; Renna et al., 2017; Sealey et al., 2011). BSFL can even be enriched with omega-3 fatty acids by manipulating their diet, further enhancing their nutritional value for fish. EU regulations now allow the use of insect protein in aqua feeds, opening new markets for insect producers (Liland et al., 2021).

Insect Protein in Poultry Feed

While legislation in the EU currently restricts insect protein in poultry feed due to BSE concerns, research suggests its potential benefits (IPIFF, 2018). Studies have shown that BSFL meal can partially replace soybean meal or maize in poultry diets without compromising growth performance or meat quality (Cullere et al., 2018). In fact, BSFL supplementation may even enhance the nutritional value of poultry meat by increasing its amino acid content (Cullere et al., 2018). Furthermore, BSFL can be naturally reared on poultry manure, offering a closed-loop waste management system (Cullere et al., 2018).

Insect Protein in Pig Feed

BSFL larvae also hold promise as a partial replacement for soybean meal in pig feed (Florou-Paneri et al., 2014). Studies suggest that BSFL can improve gut health and immune response in pigs, potentially reducing diarrhea and improving welfare (Ipema, Bokkers, Gerrits, Kemp, & Bolhuis, 2021). While further research is needed to explore the cost-effectiveness of BSFL compared to traditional protein sources like soybean meal, its potential benefits warrant further investigation (Hong & Kim, 2022).

BSF Frass (A Nutrient-Rich Byproduct)

Black soldier fly (BSF) larvae convert organic waste streams like manure and food waste into insect biomass. The leftover material after larval feeding is called frass (Elissen, Weide, & Gollenbeek, 2023). The composition of frass varies depending on the original substrate used for feeding the larvae, particularly in terms of phosphorus (P), potassium (K), and micronutrients (Lopes, Yong, & Lalander, 2022).

BSF frass is a valuable resource due to its content of nitrogen (N), P, K, organic matter, and chitin (from larval molts) (D.

Beesigamukama et al., 2022). Studies have shown that BSF frass has significantly higher N and K content compared to frass from other insects (Beesigamukama et al., 2022). However, frass breaks down quickly and may contain substances that can harm plants. Its high P content means additional nitrogen is often needed for balanced fertilization (Lopes et al., 2022).

BSF frass offers several potential applications. It can be used directly as a fertilizer or soil conditioner, composted before application, or even used for biogas production (Hol, Elissen, & van der Weide, 2022). Research suggests that BSF frass application can lead to increased seed germination rates (Beesigamukama et al., 2022).

BSF Larvae

The unassuming black soldier fly (*Hermetia illucens*) larva is emerging as a powerful tool in waste management and sustainable resource production. These larvae, despite their name, are not pests and hold immense potential for bioconversion of organic waste streams. They are voracious feeders, capable of consuming a wide variety of organic materials like manure, food scraps, and even bio-solids (Miron et al., 2023). During their development, they transform this waste into nutrient-rich insect biomass, a valuable source of protein for animal feed and other applications (Miron et al., 2023).

However, BSF larvae have the following useful products:

BSFL Oil

Oil extracted from BSFL larvae is a valuable energy source for animals due to its high content of medium-chain fatty acids. Lauric acid, a prominent fatty acid in BSFL oil, possesses antimicrobial properties that can benefit gut health (Bogevik, Seppänen-Laakso, Samuelsen, & Thoresen, 2022). While BSFL oil shows promise for specific applications, further research is needed to optimize its use in various animal feeds (Kim et al., 2020).

BSF Protein Meal

The protein meal derived from BSFL larvae is a high-quality feed ingredient containing essential

amino acids, lipids, and micronutrients that can benefit animal health (Rawski, Mazurkiewicz, Kierończyk, & Józefiak, 2021). As mentioned in the previous part BSF meal can be used in various animal feed and aquaculture applications.

Dried Larvae

Research suggests that BSF larvae meal can be a valuable and cost-effective addition to animal feed, offering a rich source of protein (Edea, Tesfaye, Yirgu, & Alewi, 2022). Protein is essential in animal diets, playing a critical role in building body tissues and supporting vital metabolic processes like enzyme function, hormone production, and antibody formation (Beski, Swick, & Iji, 2015). Insects, like BSF larvae, hold promise as a sustainable protein source for animal feed due to their economic advantages, lower environmental impact, potential for large-scale production, and efficient conversion of feed into usable biomass.

Black Soldier Fly circular economy

The black soldier fly (BSF) emerges as a key bioconversion agent within the framework of a circular bio-economy. Its role transcends mere waste management, fostering a closed-loop system characterized by efficient resource utilization and minimized waste generation within the agricultural sector.

Waste Stream Valorization through Bioconversion

The current linear economic paradigm relegates organic waste streams (food scraps, manure, and yard trimmings) to landfills. These environments promote anaerobic decomposition, a process that releases methane, a potent greenhouse gas. BSF larvae offer a compelling solution. Functioning as detritivores, they exhibit a remarkable capacity to bioconvert these very waste streams. This bioconversion process transforms what was once considered waste into valuable products:

Nutrient-Enriched Bio-fertilizer: BSF frass, the byproduct of larval digestion, is a rich source of nutrients and organic matter. Scientific studies

have demonstrated its efficacy as a soil amendment, promoting improvements in soil health, fertility, and plant growth when compared to traditional fertilizers (Lopes et al., 2022). This bio-fertilizer displaces the need for synthetic fertilizers often produced through energy-intensive processes.

Sustainable Insect Biomass as Animal Feedstock: BSF larvae themselves are a hidden gem within the bioconversion process. They constitute a protein-rich and nutritionally sound feed source for poultry, fish, and pigs. This offers a significant ecological advantage over traditional protein sources such as fishmeal and soy. Fishmeal production is often linked to overfishing, while soy production can contribute to deforestation. By incorporating BSF larvae into animal feed regimens, we can alleviate pressure on these critical ecosystems while simultaneously providing a sustainable alternative within animal agriculture (Dennis Beesigamukama et al., 2020).

Fostering a Closed-Loop Bio resource System

While the notion of "design for disassembly and reuse" traditionally applies to physical products, the BSF system champions a similar principle within the agricultural cycle. Organic waste generated during one stage (food production) becomes the sustenance for BSF larvae. Subsequently, the outputs from the BSF system (frass and larvae) transform into valuable resources for other parts of the cycle (soil health and animal feed). This creates a closed-loop bio-resource system that minimizes waste generation and maximizes resource utilization within the agricultural sector.

Resource Conservation and Ecological Stewardship

The circular bio-economy emphasizes minimizing reliance on virgin materials. BSF larvae play a pivotal role in achieving this objective. By diverting organic waste streams from landfills and converting them into usable products like frass and protein-rich feed, BSF technology reduces the need for virgin resources such as synthetic fertilizers and traditional

protein sources for animal feed. This promotes long-term resource conservation and fosters a more ecologically responsible agricultural system.

Potential for Cascading Ecological Benefits

The ecological benefits of BSF technology extend beyond the immediate advantages of waste reduction and resource recovery. BSF can

contribute to a more sustainable food system by providing a sustainable protein source for animal feed. Animals raised on BSF larvae potentially have a lower environmental footprint than those raised on traditional feed sources. Additionally, using frass as a soil amendment can lead to increased agricultural yields, further contributing to a more efficient and sustainable food system.

Figure 1. Circular BSF Operations

Source: Chineme et al., 2023

Challenges and Benefits

The growing global population, increasing wealth, and urbanization create a surge in demand for animal protein, particularly in Asia and Africa (Smith & Barnes, 2015). This puts a strain on already limited resources like fishmeal and soybean meal used in livestock feed (van Huis, 2013). BSF larvae offer a sustainable,

protein-rich alternative to these traditional feed sources.

Here's a breakdown of the opportunities associated with BSF products:

Sustainable and Cost-Effective Animal Feed

BSF larvae meal is a cost-effective and nutritious protein source for animals.

BSF production is more economical than traditional protein sources due to its lower environmental impact and potential for large-scale production.

The global feed market for poultry, pigs, fish, and pets is projected to be massive, and BSF-based feeds can significantly contribute to meeting this demand while minimizing environmental impact (Dobermann, Swift, & Field, 2017).

Waste Reduction and Upcycling

BSF larvae can convert organic waste streams like food scraps and manure into valuable products like protein-rich feed and organic fertilizer (Abro, Kassie, Tanga, Beesigamukama, & Diiro, 2020).

This promotes a circular bio-economy by reducing reliance on landfills and creating valuable resources from waste (Gärttling, Kirchner, & Schulz, 2020).

BSF Frass Fertilizer

BSF frass, a byproduct of larval digestion, is a nutrient-rich organic fertilizer containing beneficial microbes (Bortolini et al., 2020).

Studies have shown that BSF frass improves plant growth and yield compared to commercial organic fertilizers (D. Beesigamukama et al., 2022).

BSF frass fertilizer can increase farmer profits by 5-15 times compared to using BSF for feed production alone.

Livelihood Opportunities

BSF farming can diversify income for small-scale farmers, particularly women, in rural areas.

BSF production can be scaled up to create local markets and potentially export opportunities.

Reduced Reliance on Imported Feed

Smallholder farmers can use BSF as a low-cost protein source for their poultry and aquaculture, reducing dependence on expensive imported feed.

Environmental Benefits

BSF farming has a lower environmental footprint than traditional livestock production.

BSF production requires less land and water than conventional livestock (Miglietta, De Leo, Ruberti, & Massari, 2015).

BSF helps to recycle nutrients from food waste, reducing greenhouse gas emissions and soil/water contamination (Lopes et al., 2022).

Despite the several benefits possessed by BSF, there are significant challenges faced too and need to be addressed for widespread adoption as listed below:

Legal Framework

Regulations around insect-based animal feed are still evolving, and consumer acceptance needs to improve (Alhujaili, Nocella, & Macready, 2023). Legal restrictions on insect use in animal feed vary by region (Committee, 2015).

Production Challenges

Establishing cost-effective production techniques for BSF larvae at scale is crucial.

Standardization

Globally standardized regulations are needed to facilitate the international trade of BSF products.

Cost Competitiveness

High production and operational costs, competition from established feed sources like fishmeal, and ensuring consistent nutrient quality in BSF larvae are hurdles to overcome.

Moisture Content

High moisture content in BSFL frass can hinder separation from larvae, reduce efficiency, and create unfavorable conditions for plant growth (Lalander, Ermolaev, Wiklicky, & Vinnerås, 2020).

Composting Immaturity

BSF frass may not be fully composted due to high moisture content, potentially affecting its fertilizer value (Surendra et al., 2020).

Pathogen Risk

BSF frass may harbor harmful pathogens from the substrate used to feed the larvae, requiring proper treatment (Kawasaki, Kawasaki, Hirayasu, Matsumoto, & Fujitani, 2020).

Nutrient Profile

The nutrient composition of BSF can be variable and may not meet the specific needs of all crops (Gebremikael, Wickeren, Hosseini, & De Neve, 2022). Consistent quality control measures are needed.

Regulation and Standards

Regulations for using insect frass as fertilizer are not yet established in many regions.

Consumer Acceptance

Overcoming skepticism from farmers and consumers regarding the safety and efficacy of BSF frass fertilizer is essential (Poveda, 2021).

Scalability and Cost-Effectiveness

Scaling up frass production to meet agricultural demands and ensuring cost-effectiveness for large-scale use requires further research (D. Beesigamukama et al., 2022).

Storage

Maintaining proper storage conditions to prevent nutrient degradation in BSF frass over time is important.

Conclusion

Black Soldier Fly (BSF) offers a compelling solution for a multifaceted challenge: securing sustainable protein sources for animal feed, managing organic waste streams, and fostering a circular bio-economy. BSF production systems can be adapted to various scales and environments, while the derived products offer a nutritious and eco-friendly alternative to traditional protein sources. The BSF circular economy model promotes resource conservation and ecological benefits, with the potential to create a more sustainable food system. Despite ongoing efforts to optimize production methods and increase market

acceptance, BSF's potential as a key player in sustainable agriculture and waste management remains clear. However, further research is crucial to comprehensively assess the long-term environmental and social impacts of large-scale BSF farming. Addressing these challenges through continued research will ensure the safety, quality, and economic viability of BSF products for both animal feed and fertilizer applications.

Future Perspectives

The potential of Black Soldier Fly (BSF) technology extends far beyond its current applications.

1. Waste Stream Integration of BSF production with other organic waste streams, such as food waste or manure from specific livestock operations. If done this would broaden the waste management capabilities of BSF technology thus expanding the BSF circular economy.
2. Biogas and Electricity Generation since BSF production facilities could potentially capture methane emissions and convert them into biogas or electricity, further contributing to a closed-loop sustainable system.
3. Genetic Optimization where research on BSF genetics could focus on developing strains optimized for specific product outputs. For example, breeding BSF with higher protein content in larvae or increased oil production could enhance their value for different applications.
4. Advancements in automation and technologies can improve BSF production efficiency and reduce costs. Research in this area can significantly impact the scalability and economic viability of BSF technology.
5. Strategies for educating consumers about the benefits of BSF-derived products are crucial. Highlighting the environmental advantages and nutritional value of BSF protein can address potential squeamishness regarding insects as a food source hence addressing market and consumer acceptance concerns.

6. Addressing regulatory hurdles and safety considerations related to BSF products for animal feed applications in different regions is essential for smooth market entry. Collaborations between researchers, industry stakeholders, and regulatory bodies can help establish clear guidelines for safe and sustainable BSF production.

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Author Contribution

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